

predators of eggs of this insect.

N. maeander is found only in Africa. It was first observed by Fennah (1958) in Sudan and French Guinea. Later, Critchley (1977) observed the insect in Ibadan. In Sep 1983 the insect was observed in Badeggi, at a research station of the National Cereal Research Institute.

N. maeander is a potential pest of rice in Africa.

The white fly *Aelurocybotus indicus* David and Subramaniam was found in Senegal, Upper Volta, Nigeria, and Mauritania by Williams and Dips (1981). White fly is an important rice pest in some West African countries. From Feb to Apr

1983, irrigated rice from seedling to maturity at Ibadan was infested. When infestation was high, black sooty mold developed on the leaves, which eventually withered and died. Seriously affected cultivars were TOs 6865, TOs 5827, and TOx 891-212-2-102-1-1. □

Hopperburn caused by whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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WBPH (*Sogatella furcifera* Horvath) population buildup, with 15-35 insects/hill, began the first week of Sep 1983 and reached epidemic levels of 200 to 500

Area and extent of damage by WBPH at different localities in 1983 kharif in the Punjab.

District	Block	Villages affected (no.)	Area infested (ha)	Level of infestation
Patiala	Patiala	7	64	Severe
	Sirhind	29	480	Very severe
	Bhunerheri	5	36	Moderate
	Bassi Pathana	14	172	Severe
	Naba		48	Moderate
Rupar	Chamkaur Sahib	10	200	Very severe
	Total	69	1000	

insects/hill by 20 Sep. About 1,000 ha of rice in the Punjab were hopperburned. PR106 was most seriously damaged, with

10-40% grain yield reduction. Area and level of infestation are given in the table. □

Nomenclature changes for some rice arthropods

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Seed bugs

In a recent review of the seed bug genus *Stollia* Ellenrieder, *Eusarcoris* Hahn became synonymized by *Stollia* (Hsieh et al 1977. A handbook for the determination of the Chinese Hemiptera-Heteroptera). Therefore, the correct names of the species formerly under *Eusarcoris* are

- Stollia capitatus* (Distant)
- Stollia guttiger* (Thunberg)
- Stollia montivagus* (Distant)
- Stollia parvus* (Distant)
- Stollia ventralis* (Westwood)

Mole crickets

The revision of the Afrotropical mole crickets redefined the distribution of *Grylotalpa africana* Palisot de Beauvois. Townsend stated that *G. africana* is confined to Africa and does not occur in Australia or Asia (Townsend, B. C. 1983. A revision of the Afrotropical mole crickets, Bull. Br. Mus. (Nat. Hist.), Entomol. 46(2): 183). *Grylotalpa orientalis* Burmeister now replaces

G. africana in Asia. The correct name for the Asian mole cricket is *Grylotalpa orientalis* Burmeister.

Larval parasites

Mason (1981) reclassified the subfamily Microgastrinae that contains important parasitic genera – *Apanteles* and *Microgaster* – and split *Apanteles* into several new genera. Thereafter, *Apanteles* became synonymized by *Cotesia*. The correct names for the stem borer parasites *A. flavipes* (Cameron) and *A. ruficrus* Haliday are now *Cotesia flavipes* Cameron and *Cotesia ruficrus* (Haliday).

In the same reclassification, *Apanteles schoenobii* Wilkinson became the type of a new genus *Exoryza* Mason and therefore, its valid name is *Exoryza schoenobii* (Wilkinson). Similarly, *Microgaster russatus* Haliday was designated type of *Hygroplitis* Thomson. Its correct name now is *Hygroplitis russatus* (Haliday).

Pupal parasite

Joseph et al (1973) studied the oriental *Brachymeria* and reported that *Brachymeria lasus* (Walker, 1841) and *B. obscurata* (Walker, 1874) were conspecific. *B. lasus* (Walker) was published 33 yr earlier than the latter and is, therefore, the correct name for both species.

Breeding methods for Pipunculidae (Diptera), endoparasites of leafhoppers

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Pipunculid larvae are endoparasites of several Hornoptera families, especially Cicadellidae and Delphacidae, many of which are serious rice pests. We raised *Pipunculus campestris* Ltr., *Eudorylas subterminalis* Collin, and *Tomosvaryella sylvatica* Meig. in captivity at the Zoological Institute, West Berlin.

The breeding box measured 45 × 30 × 20 cm. The lid and two opposing sides were covered with a fine-gauge mesh to facilitate air flow. The two other sides were covered with glass. One glass side could be opened and closed. In the bottom of the box was a round 11-cm-diameter hole through which a potted host plant was inserted (see figure). The box was kept dry and clean to limit fungal infection of the emergent parasitic larvae.

Adult *Euscelis incisus* (Kib.), a species of cicadellid leafhopper (GLH) parasitized by the Pipunculidae species were collected by sweep net during summer and fall 1976 to 1980 from different